

VALKYRIES

D3.1 Report on relevant ethical legal societal challenges

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an analysis on relevant ethical legal societal issues met within the VALKYRIES Consortium during the project. It includes their assessment under the hard law and soft law reconstructed framework. In particular, the document highlights the role of the accountability principle as the *fil rouge* to understand the relationship between the evolution of the regulatory framework, the corresponding compliance activities, and the level of standardisation on the topic.

2. Identification

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3. Document and Project Scope

This document identifies the relevant ethical, legal and societal aspects between hard law and soft law from the VALKYRIES experience.

3.1 Project Overview

VALKYRIES aims to develop standardised and harmonised procedures for first responders. In this frame, ethical legal and societal issues shall be addressed by design to support any step of the technological development. For this reason, this deliverable will contribute to identify and assess needs of harmonisation to improve standards on these profiles.

3.2 Document Structure

This document includes a general overview of the relevant framework; the description of the issues emerged in the project; the analysis of needs of harmonisation to improve standards on these profiles.

4. Ethical, legal and societal aspects

4.1. Methodological remarks

Ethical legal and societal aspects of a research refer to a series of complementary profiles concerning the impact of a given activity on human dignity. The human-centric perspective is developed both in terms of individual and as groups protection. From this perspective, the ethical-legal compliance of a research activity is functional to address the societal challenges of the corresponding results.

In order to select the aspects arising in the development of technologies aiming to be applied within emergency contexts to coordinate first responders' actions, we collected data among the Consortium in synergies with T1.5 and WP8 and then we compared them with the literature on the topic, analysed in WP3.

In particular, during the continuous ethical-legal assessment of the project activities, the ethical-legal unit (SSSA) detected the relevant Ethical, Legal and Societal Aspects (ELSA) in Research & Development & Innovation (R&D&I) sectors by providing tailored advice to accomplish to the applicable framework. In addition, partners have been asked to fill a matrix describing the perceived societal issues emerging in VALKYRIES. This helped the task leader to better understand how compliance activities could become an enabler for standardisation on ELSA profiles as well.

In parallel, a deep analysis of the parallel experiences provided by public and private organisations has been undertaken in order to understand the level of harmonisation of the compliance procedures as well as to compare them with the development of technical and policy standards.

4.2. Ethical, legal, and societal aspects in VALKYRIES

The ethical-legal compliance activities in VALKYRIES provided a useful parameter to analyse the relationship between the three grounds of the human-centric perspective in technology and innovation, namely: ethics, law, and societal aspects.

As provided in the self-ethical assessment and in WP8 and T1.5, the VALKYRIES ecosystem is strongly related to the interoperability challenge both in the technical and legal dimensions. In particular, to manage cross-border emergencies would be necessary to enable personal and non-personal data flows with sophisticated solutions that could respond to different legal frameworks and different technical requirements to get the highest level of availability, confidentiality, and integrity. The purpose to harmonise and standardise procedures cannot avoid to consider to address case-by-case the possible exposure of end-users and data subjects' rights to specific processing of a big amount of data, possibly revealing sensitive information. VALKYRIES will not directly engage participants in the use-cases, but it aims to make available a series of solutions that could concretely process real data.

From this perspective, the ethical-legal unit provides advice both for strict compliance among the VALKYRIES life-cycle under T1.5 and WP8 together with the Project Coordinator. It contributes to the standardisation and harmonisation analysis at EU level on the ethical and legal implications of the technological solutions considering the EU current regulatory challenges and strategies that are framing the VALKYRIES context.

To this end, we mapped the EU legislative initiatives that are impacting on ethical and legal compliance and that could be applied in the scenarios designed in VALKYRIES. Then we analysed them in terms of barriers respect to the harmonisation purposes and the learned lesson from VALKYRIES.

The table below identifies for each ethical legal issue the applicable framework and the connected regulatory challenge to shape an inclusive society able to deal with the datafication of society and digitalisation of services and products. The table also describes how the multitude of complementary initiatives at EU and national levels raised both barriers against a harmonised approach in dealing with ELSA, and opportunities, mainly addressed by soft-law tools, that could contribute to align standards and practices.

Ethical legal issues and applicable framework	EU regulatory challenges	Barriers to harmonisation	Opportunities emerging from VALKYRIES
Protection of personal data are regulated by the EU Regulation 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR, and national implementations that could introduce national safeguards for special categories of data	EU Health Data Space https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en EU Data Strategy https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data	Technology development goes faster than legislative initiatives. Legal interoperability is more complex than technical one. The same technology could require different safeguards to comply with national provisions.	Principle of accountability could cover existing gaps by applying crossed interpretations arising from the interplay between regulation, standardisation, and compliance processes. Soft law regulation could contribute to standardisation
Open data and Open science under the EU Directive 2019/1024	EU Open Data Strategy https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-data	Needs to mitigate risks of dual use or misuse of results may impose limits to open data in order to avoid the manipulation of information for military/abusive purposes	Development of standardised Data Management Plans (DMP) to classify and curate research data as open as possible and as close as necessary
Trustworthiness for AI-based and technological solutions	Shaping EU Digital Future https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai	Technology development goes faster than legislative initiatives. Fragmented self-regulation initiatives	Principle of accountability satisfied by following soft law tools and self-regulation initiatives (e.g. ALTAI checklist,

Ethical legal issues and applicable framework	EU regulatory challenges	Barriers to harmonisation	Opportunities emerging from VALKYRIES
		/ isolated practices development	H2020 ethical clearance)

Table 1 – Ethical legal and societal framework

From the internal assessment, it emerged that barriers against harmonisation are mainly due to the fragmentation of the applicable framework and the misalignment between the technological progress and the introduction of binding rules. More details on these aspects are included in D1.4, here to be considered as fully recalled.

As far as this document is concerned, it is crucial to highlight how the regulatory challenges adopted by the EU Commission are perceived within the VALKYRIES consortium i) to detect practical barriers against standardisation; ii) to identify possible opportunities to boost the harmonisation; iii) to develop methodologies to comply with them, regardless the existence of binding provisions.

As a result, in fact, to comply with both hard law and soft law provisions answers to the accountability principle, that is binding under article 5 GDPR, and performs as a standard in the ongoing legislative initiatives. Therefore, following an accountable approach constitutes the common core for compliance activities in ELSA profiles. To this end, it is necessary to understand what is meant for “accountable approach” during the life-cycle of a technological solution development and how such a standard could be the procedural one to concretely achieve the goals established by the EU strategies for R&D&I.

4.3. Societal challenges under the EU Commission agenda

VALKYRIES project has been funded under the H2020 programme but it runs also in the first years of application of Horizon Europe, where the human-centric perspective in Research & Development & Innovation sectors has been particularly improved thanks to the efforts of the institutions, market players, and policy makers to undertake regulatory, standardisation, and compliance activities following an accountable methodology based on risks detection and mitigation.

In particular, the societal challenges under H2020 programme referred to i) Health, Demographic Change and Wellbeing; ii) Food security, Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry, Marine, Maritime and Inland water research; iii) Secure, Clean and Efficient Energy; iv) Smart, Green and Integrated Transport; v) Climate Action, Environment, Resource efficiency and Raw materials; vi) Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative and reflective societies; vii) Secure Societies- protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens. These challenges evolved in Horizon Europe programme into global ones related to Digital, Industry & Space Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Societies; Civil Security for Society; Health; Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment; Climate, Energy and Mobility to boost European Industrial Competitiveness.

Societal challenges are not only articulated into several sectors, but they are considered as global ones. In parallel, some ethics requirements introduced in H2020 in terms of self-assessment are now binding in Horizon Europe and developed as an additive work package also in VALKYRIES (WP8). These initiatives help to arise awareness on the ethics by design and ethics

by default approaches through the introduction of monitoring mechanisms aiming to make the given project consortium accountable. In short term, even if some EU strategies have not entered into force yet, the one-to-one ethical legal clearance required by the funding body develops ensures to address ELSA by design and by default.

From this perspective, a great contribution to standardisation on ethical, legal, and societal profiles has been provided by the projects funded by EU Commission programmes in the last years strongly impacting on policy and law making on digitalisation. In addition, independent organisations and / or authorities developed tools to establish a more fluent dialogue between players.

The table below analyses some of these initiatives aimed to standardise ethical, legal and societal profiles in R&D&I sectors together with other institutional ones.

Initiative	Issue	Tool developed	Topic
PANELFIT GA 788039	Data Protection	Guidelines on biometrics data processing https://guidelines.panelfit.eu/biometrics/exposition-and-step-by-step-guidelines/checklists/	Guidelines, Checklists and reports are developed considering the GDPR compliance perspective in research.
	Data protection and AI	Checklist on business understanding https://guidelines.panelfit.eu/ai/step-by-step/annex-iii-checklists/	
	Data protection and geolocation	Checklist on geolocation https://guidelines.panelfit.eu/geolocation/annex-checklists/	
	Security and Cybersecurity	Report on Cybersecurity in ICT research projects https://guidelines.panelfit.eu/security-and-cybersecurity/	
	Social networks	Report on Social networks for research purposes: ethical and legal requirements regarding data protection https://guidelines.panelfit.eu/social-networks/	
PANELFIT GA 788039 complementing SHERPA GA 786641	AI	Guidelines on AI https://guidelines.panelfit.eu/ai/ Guidelines for the Ethical Use of AI and Big Data Systems https://www.project-sherpa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/use-final.pdf	
EOSC-Pillar GA 857650	Open Data and Open Science	EOSC-Pillar Legal Compliance Guidelines for Researchers: a Checklist https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/eosc-pillar-legal-compliance-guidelines-researchers-checklist	It deals with both personal and non-personal data protection requirements and intellectual property rights for researchers

Initiative	Issue	Tool developed	Topic
UNESCO	Ethics of AI	Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000381137	They are addressed to Member States for regulatory purposes not to researchers for compliance
EDPB	Data Protection	European Data Protection Board - Twenty-third Plenary session: EDPB adopts further COVID-19 guidance https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020XC0417(08)	Limited to COVID-19 related data processing.
CNIL	Data Protection	Q&A https://www.cnil.fr/fr/recherche-scientifique-hors-sante-les-questions-reponses-de-la-cnil	Limited to France. Similar Q&A are published by other EU Data Protection Authorities
EUREC	Research Ethics	European Network for Research Ethics Committees (EUREC): http://www.eurecnet.org/index.html	Network that brings together already existing national Research Ethics Committees (RECs) associations, networks or comparable initiatives on the European level.
ENERI	Research Ethics	European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity (ENERI): https://eneri.eu/	Establishes an operable platform of actors in the fields of research ethics and research integrity.
EnTIRE	Research Ethics	Mapping Normative Frameworks for Ethics and Integrity of Research (EnTIRE): http://www.eurecnet.org/eurec_projects/entire.html	The aim is to create a platform that makes the normative framework governing Research Ethics and Research Integrity (RE+RI) easily accessible, supports

Initiative	Issue	Tool developed	Topic
			application in research and evaluation.
SHERPA	Research Ethics	Shaping the ethical dimensions of smart information systems (SIS), a European perspective (SHERPA): https://www.project-sherpa.eu/	Investigate, analyse and synthesise the ways in which smart information systems impact ethics and human rights issues.
ETHNA	Research Ethics	Ethics Governance System for RRI in Higher Education, Funding and Research Centres (ETHNA System): https://ethnasystem.eu/	Implement and enforce an internal management and procedural system of the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).
ROSIE	Research Ethics	Responsible Open Science in Europe (ROSIE): https://rosie-project.eu/	Provide an analysis and develop practical tools aimed at ensuring ethics and research integrity in open science and citizen science.
TechEthos	Research Ethics	Ethics for Technologies with High Socio-Economic Impact (TechEthos): https://www.techethos.eu/	Deal with the ethics of new and emerging technologies anticipated to have high socio-economic impact.
European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity	Research Integrity	Framework for self-regulation across all scientific and scholarly disciplines and for all research settings: https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/	The European Commission recognises the Code as the reference document for research integrity for all EU-funded research projects and as a model for organisations and researchers across Europe.

Initiative	Issue	Tool developed	Topic
ALTAI	Ethics of AI	ALTAI Tool helps organisations understand what Trustworthy AI is, in particular what risks an AI system might generate: https://altai.insight-centre.org/	The ALTAI tool aims to provide a basis evaluation process for Trustworthy AI self-evaluation.
RRI	Research Ethics	Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI): https://rri-tools.eu/about-rri	RRI entails engaging all actors through inclusive, participatory methodologies in all stages of R&I processes and in all levels of R&I governance.

Table 2 – Ethical legal compliance for researchers

The following remarks can be extracted from the analysis of the existing tools on ELSA profiles.

Firstly, the GDPR compliance boosted an extensive application of the principle of accountability beyond the strict data protection compliance. In particular, soft law mechanisms introduced procedures and practices to address ethical, legal and societal issues in a human-centric perspective, asking the principal investigator/the innovator/the developer to justify actions to protect fundamental rights.

Therefore, in order to be accountable, and avoid sanctions, the innovator has to prove to have implemented all the technical and organisational measures to mitigate risks to violate data subjects’ rights under the GDPR. In addition, in order to comply with the funding programme and the ethical framework, the same methodological approach requires the innovator to assess risks beyond data protection. At this stage, to comply with GDPR is not sufficient even if some legislative initiatives on AI, Machinery Products etc are not into force.

The ethical compliance, indeed, could be addressed also by the procedures to get an approval by the competent ethical committee. They are binding in certain cases, and only suggested in other ones. The methodological path to follow is also described in the protocols developed under D1.4. For the purposes of this document, indeed, it is sufficient to highlight that a barrier to standardisation and harmonisation on ELSA profiles is also given by the fact that each ethical committee develops own regulations at local level. A paradox encountered also in VALKYRIES refers to the fact that technological interoperability is easier than the legal one and sometimes it requires less efforts in terms of safeguards implementation than the costs for identifying the applicable ethical legal framework to comply with.

In this regard, the incentives towards ethical-legal compliance provided by funding programmes strongly contributed to share awareness among investigators/developers/innovators, collect best practices, and develop useful tools aiming to standardise efforts in a learning-by-doing process that is the result of an aware development of a given research. Conversely, supra-national organisations activities on the topic are mainly addressed to governments or to provide answers to specific questions without deepening the entire context. Moreover, all produced

mechanisms of standardisation have the limit not be updated to the effective evolution of the legal framework, that is –indeed- continuously evolving.

From this perspective, a standardisation process of the ethical, legal, and societal compliance activities requires an established state of the art from a regulatory viewpoint. Before the complexity and continuously evolving technical and legal progress a case-by-case adaptation is still needed in each R&D&I life-cycle.

To this end, we analysed how the standardisation in corporate governance and management systems could impact on the standardisation of ELSA profiles.

4.3.1. Standards Operation Procedures and ISO for ethical legal compliance

In order to verify the ground of standardisation of ethical legal societal compliance activities, we focused on the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and ISO standards developed for ethics compliance.

SOPs refer to procedures that illustrate the mandatory operational steps and instructions to be followed in relation to given processes or policies. SOPs are generally drafted by staff directly involved with the given process. While ISOs are developed by the ISO independent, non-governmental international organization.

The table below shows the results of the SOPs and ISO collection, impacting on ethical legal compliance in the context of R&D&I sectors.

SOP/ISO	Issue	Comment
EFSA Data Collection and Validation 2018 https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/corporate_publications/files/SOP-008_S2.pdf	Data Protection	Internal roles and responsibilities are included for each action to be taken. No reference to the legal principles. No reference on how developing a given activity.
SOPs4RI GA 824481 https://sops4ri.eu/deliverables/	Research integrity	Internal roles and responsibilities are included for each action to be taken. Templates are aimed to identify roles in a given research.
University of Birmingham https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/news/2020/qms-four-new-sops	Clinical Research	They provide clinicians templates for ethics committees' approval of given clinical studies.
Tusla Research Ethics Committee	Research Ethics Committee	They refer on the internal management of protocols submission to receive ethics clearance for studies.

SOP/ISO	Issue	Comment
https://www.tusla.ie/uploads/content/REC_SOP_-_Review_final_10092021.pdf		
EMA, https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/sop/standard-operating-procedure-compliance-check-agreed-paediatric-investigation-plan_en.pdf	Compliance in paediatric investigations	It is a check list to verify if the compliance activities have been carefully undertaken
ISO ICS 03.100.02 https://www.iso.org/ics/03.100.02/x/	Governance and ethics Including anti-bribery, anti-procurement fraud, corporate social responsibility	<p>They include the following published ISO:</p> <p>IWA 26:2017 Using ISO 26000:2010 in management system</p> <p>ISO/IEC TS 17021-13:2021</p> <p>ISO 26000:2010 Guidance on social responsibility</p> <p>ISO 26030:2019 Social responsibility and sustainable development</p> <p>ISO 37000:2021 Governance of organisations</p> <p>ISO 37001: 2016 Anti-bribery management systems</p> <p>ISO 37002:2021 Whistleblowing management systems</p> <p>Mainly related to social responsibilities and ethics in management systems.</p> <p>In addition:</p> <p>ISO 37301:2021 Compliance management systems</p> <p>They include how to establish and maintain a culture of compliance in a given organisation, introducing the following steps within the life-cycle of the compliance plan, do, check, act, regardless the provision to comply with.</p> <p>They include the following under development ISO:</p> <p>ISO/DIS 37004 Governance of organisations – Governance maturity model</p> <p>ISO/CD 37007 Corporate governance – guidelines for efficiency measurement.</p> <p>They are related to an ethical governance of a given organisation.</p> <p>ISO/CD 53800 Guidelines for the promotion and implementation of gender equality.</p>

SOP/ISO	Issue	Comment
		From the description it seems to promote and implement gender equality in all types of organizations, public or private, regardless of their size, location and field of activity.

Table 3 – SOPs and ISO for ethical-legal compliance

In summary, ISOs standardise compliance activities procedures providing instructions on how to govern the process in a given organisation. They also aim to raise a culture of compliance at any hierarchical level by identifying the steps of the compliance life-cycle.

The main lack consists of the fact that these ISOs are not developed to comply with a fragmented and in some cases overlapping frameworks like the ethical-legal ones. Therefore, they identify who shall be responsible to identify the given provision and the corresponding obligation to accomplish to, but they are not able to extract common procedures to solve interpretative issues.

SOPs are binding in the given organisation that develop and adopt them. Their consistency is determined also by the distribution of templates aiming to specifically identify roles, responsibilities and how to develop the drafted checklists.

In this regard, a standardisation and harmonisation contribution could be provided if the controlling authorities could promote the collection and classification of SOPs in order to extract a comprehensive checklist to be followed. In this regard, the D1.4 protocols for innovators is the result of the collected SOPs, internal procedures identified in the R&D&I sector.

4.3.2. Continuous ethical-legal assessment and societal impact

The role of ethical legal compliance in boosting standardisation mechanisms is strongly connected to describe the societal impact of R&D&I nowadays.

In fact, the multitude of the EU Commission strategies related to digitalisation, datafication, and innovation of society have as a common core the purpose to shape an inclusive digital society.

Since the results of technological R&I&D is part of the EU economy and of the EU citizens' daily routine, the societal impact of each life-cycle of the research cannot be avoided neither by the ethical-legal framework nor from the market.

Also in this perspective, the principle of accountability plays a crucial role: in each sector where a technology is introduced the societal impact contributes to the success of the solution. In fact, to deal with a human-centric perspective means also to look at the technological progress with the lenses of the individuals and groups of individuals that are engaged as users of a given solution.

Usability, acceptability, and feasibility are the main characteristics tested of a given technology to ensure a concrete success of the technology according to the first models developed to understand the human behaviour before the information society [Davis, 1986]. Again, these profiles are addressed only in terms of soft law unless the development of a given technology includes the engagement of participants in the validation step.

To maintain an accountable behaviour in R&D&I means to understand that the regulatory challenges aim to promote and enhance fundamental rights, not only to avoid their

infringement. In particular, the responsible research culture diffusion contributes also to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the United Nations 2030 Agenda adopted in 2015 aiming to improve health and education, reduce inequality, and spur economic growth.

The table below highlights the relationship between the EU initiatives designing the ethical legal and societal implications for R&D&I and the corresponding SDGs.

Ethical legal framework	Relationship with the SDG
Regulation (EU) no 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC (CTR)	3 Good Health and Well-being 9 Industry innovation and infrastructures 12 Responsible consumption and production 16 Peace, Justice, and strong institutions
Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation GDPR)	8 Decent work and economic growth 9 Industry innovation and infrastructures 10 Reduced inequalities 11 Sustainable cities and communities 16 Peace, Justice, and strong institutions
Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union	8 Decent work and economic growth 9 Industry innovation and infrastructures 10 Reduced inequalities 11 Sustainable cities and communities 16 Peace, Justice, and strong institutions
Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (MDR)	3 Good Health and Well-being 8 Decent work and economic growth 9 Industry innovation and infrastructures 12 Responsible consumption and production 16 Peace, Justice, and strong institutions
Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act, DGA)	8 Decent work and economic growth 9 Industry innovation and infrastructures 10 Reduced inequalities 11 Sustainable cities and communities 16 Peace, Justice, and strong institutions
Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act)	8 Decent work and economic growth 9 Industry innovation and infrastructures 11 Sustainable cities and communities 16 Peace, Justice, and strong institutions

Table 4 – Legal framework and SDG

From a legal perspective, the efforts to standardise ethical legal compliance activities are directed to develop a more responsible R&D&I achieving the global societal challenges under the 2030 Agenda.

This means that within the digital environment fundamental rights shall be not only protected but also promoted and empowered. Only through the illustrated synergies between regulation, standardisation, and compliance processes the technological progress could achieve the global societal challenges and contribute to a sustainable growth.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable described the relationships between the procedures of regulation, standardisation and compliance on the ethical legal and societal aspects of solutions developed in Research & Development & Innovation sectors.

The document included the analysis of data collected within the VALKYRIES consortium, the EU Commission current strategies, other EU funded projects and initiatives, standards developed among individual organisations and ISO.

Standardisation is currently addressed to identify common procedures to distribute responsibilities for compliance tasks and monitoring mechanisms (like checklists) to verify the accomplishment of the planned activities. These methodologies contribute to develop a culture of accountability in the R&D&I and share awareness on specific ethical legal and societal issues that a technological solution could arise.

However, none of the existing solutions are specifically addressed to cover all the ethical legal issues that an investigator/developer/innovator shall deal with. This is due to the fact that the applicable framework is often unclear both for the multitude of the current initiatives impacting on several crossed profiles and for the possible safeguards that could be introduced at national and local level as well as for specific sectors. To this end VALKYRIES is generating tailored protocols that could concretely improve the level of standardisation on the topic and contribute to reduce costs for ethical legal compliance activities.

6. Annex A – References and bibliography

Alhadeff J., Van Alsenoy B., Dumortier J., The Accountability Principle in Data Protection Regulation: Origin, Development and Future Directions, In: Guagnin, D., Hempel, L., Ilten, C., Kroener, I., Neyland, D., Postigo, H. (eds) *Managing Privacy through Accountability*. Palgrave Macmillan, London, 2011, p. 49-82, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137032225_4

Amram D., Building up the “Accountable Ulysses” model. The impact of GDPR and national implementations, ethics, and health-data research: Comparative remarks, *Computer Law & Security Review*, Volume 37, 2020, 105413, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2020.105413>.

Colangelo G., Borgogno O. (2019) Data sharing interoperability: fostering innovation and competition through APIs. *CLSR* 35:105314

Davis FD. A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: theory and results [doctoral dissertation]. Cambridge (MA): MIT Sloan School of Management; 1986.

Mantelero A (2018) AI and big data: a blueprint for human rights, social and ethical impact assessment. *CLSR* 34(4):754:772

Quinn P. (2016) The anonymisation of research data – a pyric victory for privacy that should not be pushed too hard by the EU data protection framework? *Eur. J. Health Law*. 24:1-21.

Leese M, Lidén K, Nikolova B. Putting critique to work: Ethics in EU security research. *Security Dialogue*. 2019;50(1):59-76. doi: 10.1177/0967010618809554

Vasileva, V., Application of a Human-Centric Approach in Security by Design for IoT Architecture Development. In: Gelenbe, E., Jankovic, M., Kehagias, D., Marton, A., Vilmos, A. (eds) *Security in Computer and Information Sciences. EuroCybersec 2021. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol 1596. Springer, Cham, 2022, pp.13-22, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-09357-9_2

7. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
ELSA	Ethical, Legal and Societal Aspects
R&D&I	Research & Development & Innovation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure

Table 5 – Glossary